

A Study of Understanding the Assignment and Study Environment of Undergraduate Students

Dr Sulagna Chatterjee

Assistant Professor in Education Chandraketugarh S.S Mahavidyalaya
North 24 Parganas, West Bengal, India

Corresponding author- Dr Sulagna Chatterjee

Email- chatterjeesulagna514@gmail.com

Abstract

In the educational parlance, performance manifests through academic achievement, which is the manifestation of a student's habit of study and they in turn are formed and strengthened through education. The development of good study habits is equally relative and helpful not only in academic work but in career actualization. The aim of this study is to find the relationship between understanding of assignment and study environment of undergraduate students of west Bengal. For testing hypothesis 100 students were selected randomly. Study habit scale was applied on students of Science & Humanities. Statistical analysis (both descriptive & inferential) showed significant differences between the sample group.

Keywords: Study habit, Study environment, performance, under graduate students

1.1 Introduction

Education is the most viable legacy left behind by our colonial masters. It is the only heritage transmitted to us which is well embraced because of its usefulness in shaping our society and "building" of an individual. Education enlightens and creates averseness of one's self and the world around. 21st century learning can be defined as student-centered learning. We refer to it this way because 21st century innovations make student-centered learning possible on an unprecedented scale. One must concentrate on study skills. Study skills are the skills one need to enable him / her to study and learn efficiently. Study skills, *academic skill*, or *study strategies* are approaches applied to learning. Study skills are an array of skills which tackle the process of organizing and taking in new information, retaining information, or dealing with assessments. They are discrete techniques that can be learned, usually in a short time, and applied to all or most fields of study. More broadly, any skill which boosts a person's ability to study, retain and recall information which assists in and passing exams can be termed a study skill, and this could include time management and motivational techniques.

Looking at the history of mankind, we find that each century has witnessed different transformations. Accordingly, there has been new emphasis and shift in educational processes (Mangal, 2001, p.1). Education is an activity or process, which modifies the behavior of a person from insinctive to human behavior (Taneja, 2003, p.9). This definition reveals the innate truth that education aims at discovering aptitudes as well as to progressively prepare man for social activity; because of this, education through which the basic

needs (food, shelter and clothing) are provided is necessary for the survival of the society. Simply put, performance is how well or badly something is done. Its relevance stand out because of the significance it holds to the society. In the educational parlance, performance manifests through academic achievement, which is the manifestation of a student's habit of study and they in turn are formed and strengthened through education. The development of good study habits is equally relative and helpful not only in academic work but in career actualization.

1.2 Objective of the study

1. To examine and compare the extent of understanding the assignment and study environment in undergraduate students of Science and Arts stream.
2. To examine and compare the extent of understanding the assignment and study environment in undergraduate male and female students.

1.3 Hypotheses

HO: 1.0 No significant difference exists between the mean scores in understanding the assignment of undergraduate students of Science and Arts stream.

HO: 1.1 No significant difference exists between the mean scores in understanding the assignment of undergraduate Male and Female students.

HO: 2.0 No significant difference exists between the mean scores in study environment of undergraduate students of Science and Arts stream.

HO: 2.1 No significant difference exists between the mean scores in study environment of undergraduate Male and Female students.

1.4 Definition of the terms

Understanding the assignment You've probably seen the phrase "understood the assignment" used to

death on social media. Here's why everyone is saying it. The slang term is a popular way to praise someone who is going above and beyond to do a good job.

Study environment

Study environment refers to the physical, psychological and social circumstances that as affect your wellbeing a student and how you experience your studies. The term study environment is often used, but the law often refers to students' work environment.

1.5 Methodology

Sample

The researcher selected undergraduate colleges using non-probability based purposive sampling method. The sample comprised of 100 students, selected from three institutions, namely APC College, New Barrackpore; Chandraketugarh Sahudullah Smriti Mahavidyalaya, Berachampa; Amity University, Kolkata.

1.6 Research Tools

The tool for data collection by the researcher is the standardized scale of study habit (Sen Barat,K., 1988)

Out of five dimension of the scale the researcher have taken two dimensions, namely Understanding the assignment and Study Environment.

1.7 Analysis and Discussion

The sample size of the dissertation was 100 respondents. Out of which 25 were girls and 25 were boys.25 students from Humanities and 25 students from Science stream were selected. The data was collected with the help of the tool mentioned earlier and the entire data were analyzed quantitatively. The quantitative analysis was done through descriptive and inferential statistics by dividing the total sample into two independent categories i.e., gender and stream.

Figure 1.1 Mean scores of Understanding the assignment of science and arts stream

Figure 1.2 Mean scores of Understanding the assignment of Female and Male stream

Figure 1.3 Mean scores of Study environment of Science and Arts stream

Figure 1.4 Mean scores of Study environment of Female and Male stream

Table 4.1 T- test between the mean scores of Humanities and Science students

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
Variable 1(Understanding the assignment)		
	<i>SCIENCE</i>	<i>HUMANITIES</i>
Mean	25.4	23.32
Variance	7.833333333	13.47666667
Observations	25	25
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	45	
t Stat	2.252898441	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.014593847	
t Critical one-tail	1.679427393	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.029187695	
t Critical two-tail	2.014103389	

Calculated value (2.252) is greater than table value (2.014), P value or Alpha value is less than 0.05 so the null hypothesis (HO 1.0) is rejected. It can be

said that there is significant difference between the mean scores of understanding the assignment of undergraduate students of Science and Arts stream.

Table 4.2

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances Variable 2(Study environment)		
	<i>SCIENCE</i>	<i>ARTS</i>
Mean	25.08	22.68
Variance	7.66	11.64333333
Observations	25	25
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	46	
t Stat	2.731272871	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.004458122	
t Critical one-tail	1.678660414	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.008916243	
t Critical two-tail	2.012895599	

Calculated value (2.731) is greater than table value (2.012), P value or Alpha value is less than 0.05 so the null hypothesis (HO 2.0) is rejected. It can be

said that there is significant difference between the mean scores of study environment of undergraduate students of Science and Arts stream.

Table 4.3 T test between the mean scores of boy and girl students

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances Variable 1(Understanding the assignment)		
	<i>FEMALE</i>	<i>MALE</i>
Mean	24.16	22.16
df	46	
t Stat	2.472089052	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.00859626	
t Critical one-tail	1.678660414	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.01719252	
t Critical two-tail	2.012895599	

Calculated value (2.472) is greater than table value (2.012), P value or Alpha value is less than 0.05 so the null hypothesis (HO 1.1) is rejected. It can be said that there is significant difference between the

mean scores of understanding the assignment of undergraduate students of Female and Male students.

Table 4.4

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances Variable 2(Study environment)		
	<i>FEMALE</i>	<i>MALE</i>
Mean	24.44	22.08
Variance	8.756666667	17.24333333
Observations	25	25
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	43	
t Stat	2.314170395	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.012751074	
t Critical one-tail	1.681070703	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.025502148	
t Critical two-tail	2.016692199	

Calculated value (2.314) is greater than table value (2.016), P value or Alpha value is less than 0.05 So the null hypothesis (H₀ 2.1) is rejected. It can be said that there is significant difference between the mean scores of study environment of undergraduate students of Female and Male stream.

5.0 Conclusion

The present study has focused on understanding the assignment and study environment of undergraduate students. The data was collated from students of second, fourth & six semesters respectively. The study reveals that a proper study related behavior of the students will have a positive impact on their performance. Based on the major findings of the study, it can be concluded that a good study habit certainly has an impact on the performance of the students. Most of the students are unaware of the positive impact of study habit. If the study environment is conducive then it will be of great benefit for the students learning. Therefore more emphasis needs to be laid on imparting study skill related training for the students.

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